

A STUDY ON CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR ON FAIRNESS CREAM WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO UDUMALPET TOWN

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Abstract:

The general term 'cosmetics' is applied to all preparations used externally to condition and beautify the body, by cleaning, colouring, softening, or protecting the skin, hair, nails, lips or eyes. Cosmetics are, therefore, products intended to be applied to the human body for cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness or altering the appearance without affecting the body's structure. The growth of cosmetics and beauty products markets has become significant as consumers are increasingly becoming aware of appearance, beauty, grooming and the choice of personal care products. The present study has to analyse the consumer buying behaviour towards Fairness creams to have a deep knowledge of consumer behaviour regarding fairness creams in my research I have tried to find out main brand used? Why these brands are used? Factor affecting the purchases behaviour like price, quality, results, etc. The importance gained by the individual consumer in the present market compel the marketers to look the buying habits, preferences, taste, like and dislikes of consumers and accordingly they need to revise its policies and marketing mix.

Key Words: Consumers, Buying Behaviour & Fairness Cream

Introduction:

India has now become a developed market for cosmetic players since the last decade. Currently there are several cosmetic manufacturing companies, who are operating in all kinds of cosmetics. In the entire range of products that fall within the territory of the Indian cosmetic, the most popular items are colour cosmetics, of which nail varnish, lipsticks and lip glosses account for the most sales. In this area, popular local brand names include Lakme and Revlon. Skin-care cosmetics have experienced a slower growth and products such as anti-wrinkle creams, cleansers and toners, for instance are not as popular as facial creams, moisturizers and fairness creams in this genre. The market size for fairness cream in India was estimated to be Rs.800 crore. The market growth rate ranges between 15– 20% on a year-to-year basis. The leading players in the market includes Hindustan Lever Ltd., (HLL's) 'Fair & Lovely' with 76 percent of the market share and Cavin Kare's 'Fairer' with 15 percent of the market share. Other important players like Godrej's 'Fairglow', Emami's 'Fair and Handsome', Vicco and Himalaya share the rest of the market share. It has been estimated that males constitute 20 percent of the total sales for fairness creams in India. Companies like Ponds and Fair and Lovely rule the roost in this segment. Unilever and Procter & Gamble are major players in the Indian cosmetic sector of shampoos and hair products. However, the Indian hair-care cosmetic sector now has a few foreign brands to compete with these giants as well. Finally, one of the most popular cosmetic produced in India are herbal cosmetics which have gained popularity internationally in recent years, Emami and Ayur herbal products are the most well-known in this area.

Review of Literature:

Asseal, H. (2004) conducted a study on "Marketing of consumer goods" in Vishakapatnam. It was found that large number of respondents purchased consumer products from private retail shop followed by super bazaar & consumer co-operative store and housewife played a vital role in taking purchase decision.

Atkin, C. and Martin B. (1993) conducted a survey on "Husband-Wife Involvement in Buying Decision Making". One of the major findings of the study is husband who are young, highly educated & belong to high income group are relatively less dominated than their older, less educated & low income counterparts.

Batchman, G. R, John, D. R. and Rao, A. R. (1993) "A study of Brand loyalty in India". The study concluded that Indian consumers have been found becoming more & more brand loyal. Depending upon the nature of the product, they have single or multiple brand loyalty are quality of the product, habit of use and regular availability of the product.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To know the socio-economic profile of the sample respondents
- ✓ To analyse the factors influencing the purchase decision of the respondents

Scope of the Study:

The scope of the study covers all categories of fairness creams. The whole appraisal of fairness creams will be angle of customer satisfaction. Any substitutes of fairness creams like soap or natural products will not be considered. Also fairness creams locally made by the unorganized sectors and which or not branded will not be considered.

Research Methodology:

Descriptive research design has been used for this study and a survey has been done for fact-finding inquiries of different kinds. Sampling method used for the study is convenience sampling method. A sample size is 150 respondents. The data is collected through the questionnaire. Primary data collected through face to face interviews while filling up questionnaires 150 respondents from Udumalpet town. Relevant information gathered from magazines, newspapers and project reports that formed the secondary data.

Statistical Tools:

The statistical are used in the study are:

- ✓ Simple percentage analysis
- ✓ Chi-square analysis

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study was conducted in Udumalpet. This may not give a generalized conclusion.
- ✓ The sample size is limited to 150 due to the shortage of time.
- ✓ Few respondents were reluctant file answering the question due to their busy schedule.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Socio-Economic Profile of the Respondents

S.No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percent
1	Gender	Male	47
		Female	53
2	Age	Below 25	21
		26-35 years	40
		36-45 years	22
		Above 45	17
3	Location	Rural	28
		Semi Rural	33
		Semi urban	14
		Urban	25
4	Educational Qualification	Illiterate	15
		Up to HSC	30
		Graduate	45
		Post Graduate	10
5.	Monthly Income	Below Rs.25,000	45
		Rs.25,000 to Rs.50,000	17
		Rs.50,000 to Rs. 1,00,000	21
		Above Rs .1,00,000	17
6.	Brand Used	Loreal	36
		Lakme	8
		Ponds	25
		Garnier	17
		Fair & lovely	7
		Fairever	7
7.	Usage of Brand	Last six months	61
		6 months to 1 year	13
		1 to 2 years	15
		More than 2 years	10

Source: Primary Data

From the above table Majority (53%) of the respondents are female. Majority (40%) of the respondents are age group between 26-35 years. Majority (45%) of the respondents are Graduate. Majority (33%) of the respondents are living in semi urban area. Majority (45%) of the respondents earning below Rs.25,000 per month. Majority (36%) of the respondents are using Loreal brand. Majority (61%) of the respondents are using branded fairness cream last six months.

Table 2: Factor Influencing Purchase Decision of Buying Fairness Cream

S.No	Purchase Decision of Buying Fairness Cream	Respondents	Percent
1	Price	52	35
2	Quality	30	20
3	Brand image	32	21
4	Promotional offers	14	9
5	Word of mouth	12	8

6	Availability	10	7
	Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table out of 150 respondents, 35% of the respondents are making purchase decision buying fairness cream by price, 20% of the respondents are making purchase decision buying fairness cream by quality, 21% of the respondents are making purchase decision buying fairness cream by brand image, 9% of the respondents are making purchase decision buying fairness cream by promotional offers, 8% of the respondents are making purchase decision buying fairness cream by word of mouth and remaining 7% of the respondents are making purchase decision buying fairness cream by availability. Majority (35%) of the respondents are making purchase decision buying fairness cream by price.

Chi Square Test:

Table 3: Gender and Brand Wise Classification

The following hypothesis is formulated to test the significance of relation between gender and brand.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between gender and brand.

Particular	L'Oreal	Lakme	Ponds	Garnier	Fair & Lovely	Fairever	Total
Male	30	7	19	5	6	3	70
Female	24	5	20	20	4	7	80
Total	54	12	39	25	10	10	150

d.f 4 Calculated X² value: 11.41

Table value: Five percent level: 9.49

From the above analysis, it is clear that the table value is less than calculates value null hypothesis is rejected; there is a significance association between gender and brand wise classification

Suggestions:

- ✓ A company should market exclusive cosmetic products for male consumers.
- ✓ A marketer should built up a prompt distribution channel to avoid the problem of non – availability of products.
- ✓ A proper communication should be created with doctors, beauticians and should be involved in advertisement to make them more attractive, affective and reliable.
- ✓ Marketer should include your attitude and personal appeal in their advertising communication as the consumer buy cosmetic products on their own.

Conclusion:

Fairness creams constitute a consistent proportion of income for the FMCG companies in India. As most of the people are very much bothered about their colour complexion the fairness creams enjoy very good market growth rate when compared with other related product categories. It is not sufficient if a company has the right product with right quality. It has to be communicated properly to the target audience. The modern market is highly competitive in nature. The consumer is the king in the market. The importance gained by the individual consumer in the present market compel the marketers to look the buying habits, preferences, taste, like and dislikes of consumers and accordingly they need to revise its policies and marketing mix. While purchase of cosmetic product, the consumers are found more quality conscious preferred to purchase ayurvedic products, they wait for the brand during non- availability, become emerging as important source of information and in spite of impact of other factors, the actual brand decision is taken by themselves.

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